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Xist activation occurs during metastasis in the male species.

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Measuring and capturing activation and silencing of Xist in cancer is and transformation is difficult because of sex-specific differences in Xist expression in normal tissues, due to challenges associated with the kinetics of Xist activation or silencing at the X-inactivation center, and due to organismal (individual) and tissue-specific variation in Xist transcriptional changes. We report here through next-generation sequencing of the primary and metastatic tumor transcriptomes in humans with prostate cancer that Xist activation occurs in physiologically relevant context, in the male species during metastasis.